

DOI

INKLUZJA JAKO NOWE ZJAWISKO SPOŁECZNO-EDUKACYJNE

Iryna Sadova

Doktor nauk psychologicznych, docent

Katedra Pedagogiki i Metodyki Edukacji Podstawowej

Drohobycki Państwowy Uniwersytet Pedagogiczny im. Iwana Franki,

(Drohobycz, Ukraina)

e-mail: iryna-sadova@ukr.net

ORCID ID:0000-0003-2570-5392

Streszczenie. W niniejszym artykule naukowym autorka na podstawie analizy badań podstawowych oraz ram prawnych i regulacyjnych podaje definicję nowego zjawiska społecznego i pedagogicznego – “edukacji inkluzyjnej”. Termin “edukacja inkluzyjna” w różnych źródłach poświęconych edukacji dzieci ze specjalnymi potrzebami edukacyjnymi (SPE) jest interpretowany z różnych perspektyw w organizacji procesu pedagogicznego. Autorka proponuje jedną z najczęstszych interpretacji: “Edukacja inkluzyjna - termin używany do opisanego procesu nauczania dzieci z SPE w szkole średniej ogólnokształcącej”. Uogólnienie najbardziej istotnych cech edukacji inkluzyjnej umożliwia sformułowanie przez autorkę definicji pojęcia “edukacji inkluzyjnej” w kontekście podejścia kulturowego i aksjologicznego: “Edukacja inkluzyjna jest wielowymiarowym zjawiskiem pedagogicznym, którego podstawą jest określenie wartości, wyjątkowości i różnorodności wszystkich dzieci oraz usunięcie jakichkolwiek form ich dyskryminacji w celu zapewnienia produktywnego włączenia każdego dziecka do systemu ogólnego kształcenia, co przyczynia się do jego dalszej pełnej socjalizacji”. Autorka dokonała retrospektywnej analizy problemu edukacji inkluzyjnej na podstawie uogólnienia doświadczeń krajowych i zagranicznych; scharakteryzowane zostało inkluzyjne środowisko edukacyjne szkoły jako przestrzeń wychowawcza dla rozwoju społecznego uczniów; ujawniony został zestaw pedagogicznych warunków wychowywania dzieci z SPE w inkluzyjnym środowisku edukacyjnym.

Słowa kluczowe: dzieci ze specjalnymi potrzebami edukacyjnymi, edukacja inkluzyjna, inkluzyjna szkoła, socjalizacja.

INCLUSION AS A NEW SOCIO-EDUCATIONAL PHENOMENON

Iryna Sadova

Ph.D (Psychology), Docent of Pedagogic and Methods of Primary Education

Drohobych Ivan Franko State Pedagogical University,

(Drohobych, Ukraine)

e-mail: iryna-sadova@ukr.net;

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2570-5392

Abstract. In the scientific article, the author gives the definition of a new social and pedagogical phenomenon – “inclusive education” on the basis of the analysis of the basic research and the legislative and regulatory framework. The term “inclusive education” is interpreted from different perspectives in the organization of the

pedagogical process in various sources devoted to the education of children with special educational needs (SEN). The author offers one of her most common interpretations: “Inclusive education is a term used to describe the process of teaching children with SEN in the institutions of general secondary education”. Generalization of the most significant characteristics of inclusive education makes it possible to formulate the author's definition of the concept of “inclusive education” in the context of cultural and axiological approaches: “Inclusive education is a multidimensional pedagogical phenomenon, the fundamental basis of which is the determination of the value, uniqueness and the diversity of all children and the elimination of all forms of discrimination against them, with a view to ensure the productive inclusion of each child in the general education system, which contributes to its further full socialization”. The author has made a retrospective analysis of the problem of inclusive education on the basis of the generalization of domestic and foreign experience; the inclusive educational environment of the school as an educational space for the development of students' sociality has been characterized; the complex of pedagogical conditions of upbringing the children with SEN in inclusive educational environment has been revealed.

Keywords: children with special educational needs, inclusive education, inclusive school, socialization.

Introduction. It should be noted that no issue in the history of pedagogy of special and general education causes as much scientific debate as inclusion. Inclusive education as a new educational and social phenomenon, which is the subject of numerous theoretical and practical studies, involves the identification of determinants of formation and development of its content, structural, methodological components, as well as the definition of strategies for its effective implementation.

The research, socio-cultural and practical aspects of inclusive education are extremely relevant to Ukraine, as the educational system is at the very beginning of this path. Specialists consider issues of inclusive education of children with special educational needs (SEN) especially topical, which are accompanied by problems of legal, organizational, technical, financial and social nature nowadays. In this regard, the appeal to the experience in this field, its study and critical analysis becomes timely and important for the Ukrainian education system.

Analysis of basic research and publications. Many studies are devoted to the education of children with special educational needs in conditions of inclusive education (V. Bondar, O. Bezpalko, T. Illiashenko, A. Kolupayeva, I. Lutsenko, E. Martynova, N. Malofeyev, O. Savchenko, T. Sak, V. Syniov, T. Sophii, O. Taranchenko, A. Shevtsov, A. Shevchuk, M. Sheremet). Theoretical foundations of inclusive education have been developed by such foreign scientists as D. Armstrong, H. Levin, M. Nind, M. Olver, H. Smith, A. Sander, S. Staiback, M. Winzer, D. Rogers, and others.

The purpose of the article provides the analysis of inclusive education as a new socio-pedagogical phenomenon.

Presenting the main material. The term “inclusive education” in various sources devoted to the education of children with special educational needs is interpreted from different positions in the organization of the pedagogical process. Here is one of its most common interpretations: “Inclusive education is a term used to describe the process of teaching children with special educational needs in general secondary education institutions” (*Kolupaieva, Taranchenko, 2016, p. 12*).

The Salamanca Statement defines inclusion as a reform that supports and “welcomes” the peculiarities and differences of each student in order to avoid social segregation caused by differences in race, gender, culture, social class, religion, nationality and individual abilities (*The Salamanca Statement, 1994*).

Inclusive education involves, first and foremost, a wide variety of educational needs, as well as the so-called special educational needs (SEN) (this term is enshrined in the regulatory field of Ukraine (*CMU The Resolution of November 14, 2018 № 952 “On certain categories of people with special educational needs”, 2018*).

As researchers A. Kolupaieva and O. Taranchenko emphasize, “inclusive education is a flexible, individualized system of teaching children with peculiarities of psychophysical development in the conditions of mass secondary school at the place of residence” (*Kolupaieva, Taranchenko, 2016, p. 32*).

Even the most superficial analysis of the above definitions of the phenomenon gives grounds for the conclusion that we are talking about the modernization (didactic, content, methodical, spatial, social) of general and special education. The purpose of the aforementioned educational changes is to provide conditions for inclusion of students with different backgrounds, including SEN, into the educational environment. By the way, the variability of the latter is extremely significant and wide, due to the presence of disability, certain disorders of psychophysical development (*International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health. 2001, p. 234*), disorders of behavior, and may also be caused by conditions of upbringing in the foster family, the poor social status of the family, their parents' affiliation to a particular religious denomination, the multilingualism of the child's home environment, the child's talent, etc.

The emergence of inclusive education is traced throughout the institutionalization and development of the “special school”, its organizational forms. Despite the opinion about the imperfection of special education, the researcher N. Malofeiev treats it as an unconditionally progressive phenomenon, which testifies to the cherishing of tolerant attitude in the social community towards the so-called “inferior” people, their “otherness” and determines the possible conditions for education (*Malofeiev, 2009, p. 319*).

Therefore, inclusive education is based on the fact that all children, despite their mental, intellectual, physical and other characteristics, are involved in the general education system – they are educated together with their peers at the place of residence in general secondary education institutions where they can get necessary special support and their specific educational problems are taken into account, where students' differences are treated positively and individual features are not perceived as a problem but as opportunities to enrich the process of cognition.

Scientists define three stages of rapid development of inclusive education (*Artiushenko, 2010*).

Let us briefly describe them.

The first stage – analytical – provided studying the models of education of children with SEN, understanding of such a problem.

The next, second stage of the development of educational inclusion is haphazard: it has a natural occurrence of children with SEN in the educational institutions. In addition, the absence of a correctional institution or its territorial distance from the child's place of residence, as well as misdiagnosis (or lack thereof) and the interest of general education schools in the influx of any category of students in conditions of the demographic crisis were the reasons for the so-called spontaneous inclusion.

The third stage – conceptual justification, development of a system for teaching children with SEN in educational institutions, experimental modeling – continues today. During this period, inclusive education is affected by numerous socio-cultural contradictions, namely, – between:

1. New socio-cultural and ideological circumstances that stimulate the adoption of laws to counteract discrimination against social minorities and adverse economic conditions.
2. Laws that declare the rights of a child with a disability to development and education, and the actual lack of mechanisms for their implementation.
3. The need for scientific substantiation of inclusive education and the lack of its systematic studies in pedagogy.
4. The need for a systematic approach in inclusive education that include the legal, educational, social and economic subsystems, and its implementation by extrapolation, that is, through numerous experiments and adaptation to the domestic conditions of certain foreign inclusive modifications.

An important prerequisite for the development of inclusive education in Ukraine is the awareness of the need to develop each personality as a modern school strategy, and to subordinate all structural components of the educational process to this goal. In this regard the priority determinant of educational inclusion, the following ideas emerge: a) fundamentalization that encourage philosophical and categorical analysis, rethinking and refining the general parameters and differences of normal and impaired development; b) humanization, which determines the main task of educators of full value and dignified life of a person with developmental characteristics; c) integration and inclusion, according to which joint education and upbringing of children with SEN and their healthy peers is appropriate and optimal (*Budnyk, 2015*).

As noted above, inclusion is based on the principles of humanistic psychology, humanism, which proclaim the value of individuality and provide for the obligatory consideration of one's personality traits (the position of self-concept (*Rogers, 2001, p. 414*), cognitive constructivism (*Piaget, 1983, p. 1983*). 90-101), the doctrine of the zone of immediate development (*Vyhotskyi, 1983, p.124*). The humanistic position of the teacher lies in his belief in each child, the conviction of the “presumption of competence” of the latter, the ability to “accept the student as he is”, and become an accomplice to his life.

The basis of the philosophy of inclusive education is a new social model that assumes equality of all members of society, regardless of health status, as opposed to the medical model (*Taranchenko, 2017, p. 50*), according to which a person with developmental characteristics is an object of burdensome charity, ill, requires long-term care and treatment, but in society is perceived solely through the lens of developmental disabilities. The social model, on the contrary, promotes the provision of equal opportunities for all to receive education and the equality for all children, to accept the pupils as they are, the presence of each of them a certain positive potential, and their right to visit the nearest educational institution. The social model and the concept of inclusive education were formed in the conditions of a new open society, which enables all children and adults, regardless of age, gender, developmental features, abilities, ethnicity, participation in society and a certain contribution to it. In such a society, differences are respected and appreciated.

Experts refer to the strategic direction of development of modern education as successful solving of the problems of socialization of children, determined by the conditions of organization of educational space (*Becker, 2009, p. 132*). Achieving this

goal is an important socio-cultural factor that determines the development of inclusive education practices. Without denying the value of knowledge and the need to master it in the educational process, the humanistic approach emphasizes the importance of each child's personality, his or her abilities, self-development and self-realization.

The specificity of inclusive education implies complication and expansion of social connection of children with SEN. The conditions of inclusive education most closely reflect the quality of real social relationships and processes. Thus, an inclusive educational environment certainly contributes both to the formation of a “personal choice of activities” and the expansion of a “catalog” of activities (*Leontiev, 2004, p.188*). In other words, nowadays an inclusive educational space is an important factor in the quality of socialization of children with SEN.

The evolution of social relations, their democratization and the formation of civil society determine the development of inclusive education ideas, fundamentally new approaches to the educational process. Let us list only the most important of them: 1) a priori understanding of the right of each child to receive education in the environment of their peers, which is realized in the possibility of choosing an educational route, educational institution, the content of education; 2) the recognition of the value of “otherness” when dissimilarity, a distinctive feature of a person is considered as a variant of manifestation of individuality and presupposes the presence of “other”, “special” needs, including educational ones; 3) ensuring that universal education is accessible to all children, based on their specific educational needs and individual capacities; 4) the acceptance of the subjective position of each child, the development of his personality as the main criterion for the effectiveness of the entire educational system, which provides for the definition of life prospects and related educational tasks, formulated in the form of social request of the family and the child (*Sadova, 2019, p. 93*).

Among the important social factors for the development of ideas of inclusive education, experts highlight means of culture, art, the mass media, which promote a positive image of a person with a disability, emphasizing its right to a decent life, inclusion in general education, social community, professional activity.

Socio-economic factors contribute to the development of inclusive education as well. The results of the studies (*Sadova, 2019, p. 94*) confirm the feasibility and effectiveness of joint models of learning for all children, leading to a reduction in financial costs by reducing the number of special education institutions, reinvesting released funds to meet the educational needs of all children.

The analysis of theoretical and practical aspects of inclusive education in Ukraine has revealed three levels of problems of its development – macro-level, mezo-level, micro-level (*Artiushenko, 2010*).

What is the specificity of each of them?

So-called microproblems of educational inclusion are regulated by specific organizations and professionals, individuals or stakeholders. This micro-level is related to the psychological acceptance of the pedagogical and parental community of educational institutions for children with SEN. Specialists recognize the need to overcome: discriminatory attitudes and professional stereotypes of teachers regarding children with SEN; the unwillingness of teachers to work in heterogeneous classes, and on the part of the parents of healthy students – to treat “special” children correctly; the anxiety of the parents of the latter, as well as the lack of appropriate motivation and knowledge from the teachers to work with such a category of children.

The mezo-level of inclusion problems can be traced in the fields of ideology, mass culture and social relations. The following factors significantly inhibit the realization of inclusive education tasks at this level: 1) social ideology with its priority of assimilating the educational standard rather than personal development; 2) stereotypes regarding people with disabilities; 3) intolerant attitude towards them; 4) lack of individualization in the education of children.

Macro-problems of educational inclusion are solved through the activities of state and regional legislative, political and socio-economic institutions. This macro level is related to civic and legal support for inclusive education. The main obstacles to the implementation of inclusive education at this stage are: a) non-compliance of legislation with international standards; b) imperfection of legislation on education of people with disabilities; c) lack of a unified state policy on inclusive education; d) lack of economic support for educational inclusion.

In this regard, the formation of a tolerant perception of people with disabilities, a positive public attitude to the education of children with SEN, the legal culture of the population, should be the subject of purposeful work of educators, members of the public, the media. Scientists see the main perspectives of inclusive education in the development of inclusive school policy and culture. An important aspect of the implementation of inclusive education is also the realization of programs to overcome discriminatory attitudes and professional stereotypes of teachers, the failure of parents of joint studying of “ordinary” and “special” children, the involvement of teaching specialists in the teaching staff.

The above social prerequisites and educational factors change the accents and tasks of the school as an institution of learning, upbringing, development and socialization, which, in turn, determine the extension of the professional functions of the teacher, the need to review the requirements for his professional competence. The basis for change can be considered the following humanistic principles: 1) understanding and supporting the personal development of each child; 2) the choice of individual educational trajectories by each person; 3) tolerance as a civilizational norm for the development of a particular person and social groups in the world of diversity (*Losev, 1991, p. 12*).

Therefore, the type of education analyzed today is being implemented as a model of an inclusive social community, which provides a number of benefits for different social groups. So, for children the significant advantages are:

- an opportunity for everyone to study at school at their place of residence, to communicate with their peers;
- formation of vital competences as a result of inclusive education: to perceive and understand the outside world, to behave in it properly, to realize its role and purpose; willingness and ability to navigate the society and space of culture;
- the creation of conditions for socialization in the natural educational environment;
- facilitating comprehensive interaction and communication, mastering various communication techniques and using them in communicative situations;
- the disappearance of fear in healthy children of possible disability;
- affirmation and strengthening of friendly relations in the children's collective, which will later be inherited in adulthood; confronting negative social stereotypes and discrimination.

Conclusions. Therefore, an inclusive model of the educational space should become a cultural model, the basis of which is always the a priori value of each person's

life and their right to be accepted in the social and educational community, tolerance to the varied manifestations of individuality.

In our opinion, an inclusive school is an institution with a cohesive group of like-minded people, a high level of inclusive culture; productive interdisciplinary collaboration; it is focused on deep learning about discriminatory barriers that impede the full inclusion of children in the broader educational context. Generalization of the most significant characteristics of inclusive education makes it possible to formulate the author's definition of the concept of “inclusive education” in the context of cultural and axiological approaches. Inclusive education is a multidimensional pedagogical phenomenon, the fundamental basis of which is the determination of the value, uniqueness and diversity of all children, and eliminating any form of discrimination against them, in order to ensure the productive inclusion of each child in the general education system, which contributes to its further full socialization.

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